

Transfer of Technologies by Russian Firms: Strategies and Connection to Regional Prosperity

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Abstract: The paper analyzes the strategies of Russian regional firms related to the transfer of technology. Technology transfer can be an essential driver of innovative development and contribute to sustainable economic growth. Technology transfer is usually understood as the application of technologies, methods, and knowledge developed by other organizations. Often, the active participation of enterprises in technology transfer reflects the features of their innovative behavior and the chosen strategy of innovative development. The paper analyzes the activity of Russian regional firms in technology transfer and the relationship of technology transfer and adaptation with the results of innovation activity. The results of innovation activity are understood as its scale and the quality of innovative products assessed based on market and technological product novelty. The paper considers the GRP per capita indicator as an indicator of regional well-being. The number of technologies transferred and adopted by firms and transfers from abroad of the Russian Federation is analyzed. Besides, the propensity of enterprises to interact with foreign partners in research activities is taken into account. The clustering of regions is used to identify the most widespread strategies. Clustering is conducted for three periods: 2016, 2017, and 2018. As a result, it was possible to identify five sustainable strategies of firms concerning technology transfer. Even though the strategies themselves turned out to be relatively stable, some regions are subject to strategy change, which is associated, among other things, with the cyclic nature of innovation activity. It should also be noted that the overall well-being of the region significantly influences the choice of strategy.

Keywords: innovation, innovative process, technology transfer, Russia, clusters

1. Introduction

Knowledge and innovation are key sources of sustainable competitive advantage in a global economy characterized by increasing competition and highly geographically fragmented production activities (Nolan and Pilat, 2016). The increased competition encourages companies to look for new solutions to achieve advantages. One of such solutions is technology transfer. Technology transfer can be an essential driver of innovative development (Allen et al., 2014) and contribute to sustainable economic growth (Hossain, 2012). Technology transfer is usually understood as the application of technologies, methods, and knowledge developed by other organizations (Melkers et al., 1993; Rogers, 1962).

In turn, international technology transfer, in which a party from one country gains access to knowledge whose source is in another country, is an crucial element of modernization and diffusion. Since there is a significant technological gap between firms from developed and developing countries (Fu and Zhang, 2011), international technology transfer is an important complement to the domestic sources of firms in developing countries (Grossman and Helpman, 1994). Adoption of foreign technology can play a key role in reallocating resources from less productive to more productive uses and facilitate economic and structural transformation, which has been identified as an important factor in economic growth in catching-up countries (McMillan and Rodrik, 2011).

Technology can be transferred in an embodied form, i.e., in the form of equipment or in an intangible form, which includes various knowledge and production methods (Teece, 1977). Different technologies may produce different results in terms of product quality, although they may also generate the same results at different costs. Innovation in this context can be defined as the development of new technologies that can create additional economic value (Kowalski et al., 2017). Thus, productivity, technology, and innovation are closely related.

A significant number of empirical studies are devoted to the relationship between research and development and technology transfer (e.g., Ferrantino, 1992; Hu et al., 2005). This relationship may be complementary or substitutive (Golichenko and Samovoleva, 2015). In some cases, technology acquisition contributes to the

growth of own research and development costs (Cassiman and Veugelers, 2006; Lokshin et al., 2007). At the same time, along with the impact of technology transfer on the innovative activity of the enterprise, there is also learning (Cohen and Levinthal, 1989) as a result of the application of external knowledge. Nevertheless, many studies have shown the negative impact of technology transfer on the activity of enterprises in conducting their research. This situation arises when R&D (Research and Development) and technology transfer have independent and similar effects on the knowledge base and enterprise productivity (Neelanjan, 2015). As a result, technology transfer can lead to the displacement of the internal development of the enterprise (Love and Roper 1999). At the same time, some developing countries have sought to strategically use international technology transfer policies as a development tool. For example, as a means of attracting investment and stimulating domestic innovation that can increase both the overall size of the economy and the value added per worker (Park and Lippoldt, 2008).

At the same time, a certain balance between internal and external sources of knowledge is necessary for successful innovation activities (Berchicci, 2013). The use of only technologies developed by other organizations can lead to a sharp decrease in the productivity and competitiveness of the enterprise (Grimpe and Kaiser, 2010). For this reason, among others, government policies in many countries are aimed at encouraging companies to conduct their research and development. The predominance of substitution or complementation effects is mainly due to external factors, such as the general level of wealth of the country or region and research potential (Golichenko and

Samovoleva 2015). Despite the broad evolution from restrictive to enabling policies for international technology transfer, some measures are seen as having a distorting effect on competition and have been criticized in the international context (Kowalski et al., 2017).

The paper aims to analyze the impact of technology transfer on the change in the activity of enterprises in conducting their research and development, taking into account the obtained innovation result. To answer this question, the first stage of the study analyzes the strategies of enterprises concerning technology transfer, depending on external factors. Then the connection of the obtained strategies with the activity of enterprises in carrying out their research and development is analyzed. Furthermore, as a result, the cumulative impact of technology transfer and internal research and development on the innovative activity of enterprises is analyzed.

At the first stage, the paper analyzes the activity of technology transfer of Russian regional enterprises and the relationship of technology transfer and adaptation with the results of innovation activity. The results of innovation activity are understood as its scale and the quality of innovative products assessed based on market and technological novelty of products. The second stage of the study analyzes the relationship between the identified strategies of technology transfer and activity in conducting R&D.

2. Data and research method

This paper uses data from the Russian Federal Statistical Service for 2016-2018 and data published on the official website of the Unified Information System for the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation.

To identify the most common strategies of technology transfer by regional enterprises, a clustering of Russian regions is carried out depending on the number of technologies adopted and transferred. Thus, clustering is carried out based on the following indicators:

- the ratio of the number of transferred technologies to the number of enterprises in the region (sold);
- the share of technologies transferred abroad (portion_sold);
- the ratio of the number of adopted technologies to the number of enterprises in the region (bought);
- the share of technologies adopted from abroad (portion_bought);
- the share of joint research and development projects with foreign partners (portion_RD).

Clustering was conducted three times, for 2016, 2017, and 2018, using the k-means method as the clustering method. Inertia methods, hierarchical clustering, and cluster silhouette coefficient analysis were used to select the optimal number of clusters.

As a result of the analysis for 2016, 5 clusters were obtained. At the first stage, to choose the optimal number of clusters, we considered the dependence of the sum of squares of distances from points to the centroids of clusters, to which they belong, on the number of clusters (see Fig. 1). Based on the dependence obtained, it can be assumed that the optimal number of clusters is from 5 to 7 since the decrease in the squares of distances with an increasing number of clusters decreases less intensively.

Figure 1: The dependence of the sum of squares of distances from points to cluster centres $J(C_k)$ on the number of clusters k

Next, agglomerative clustering was carried out, and a dendrogram was constructed (see Fig. 2). In the beginning, each object was placed in a separate cluster, and then the clusters were merged into larger and larger clusters until all objects were in the same cluster. In this way, a system of nested partitions was constructed. The results are presented as a tree (dendrogram). Ward's method was used to estimate distances between clusters. As a result of the hierarchical clustering, it was possible to establish that a reasonable number of clusters is 4 or 5. If Ward's distance between objects does not exceed 1.5, the number of clusters is 5.

Figure 2: Dendrogram for hierarchical clustering, 2016

Also, to select the number of clusters, a silhouette coefficient analysis was performed. The silhouette coefficient is calculated using the average intra-cluster distance (a) and the average distance to the nearest cluster (b) for each object. Silhouette is calculated as $(b - a) / \max(a, b)$. In this case, b is the distance between a and the nearest cluster, which a is not included in. In the paper, the average value of the silhouette over all objects was calculated. This allowed us to use this metric to estimate the number of clusters. The value of the silhouette coefficient shows how similar the object is to the objects of its cluster compared to other clusters. The value of the index can range from -1 to 1. Analysis of silhouette coefficients for the different number of clusters showed that the optimal choice would be five clusters (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Silhouettes at k=5

Next, we clustered the regions of the Russian Federation by k-means into five clusters. The graph of average values characterizes the average values of the indicators for each cluster and allows a comparative analysis of clusters. The graph of average values is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Graph of average values for clusters (2016)

The most significant number of regions is characterized by low activity in adopting and transferring technology (the first cluster). Nevertheless, some regions show different behavior. Thus, the regions of the second cluster tend to actively cooperate with foreign partners in research and development. At the same time, the number of technologies transferred and received is insignificant. The regions of the third cluster are characterized by their focus on the acquisition of ready-made foreign technologies with a small relative number of them. The regions of the fourth cluster sell a significant part of technologies abroad. At the same time, they are also inclined to acquire foreign technologies. The fifth cluster is characterized by many transferred and acquired technologies, and the transfer is carried out mainly within the country.

A similar way was used to cluster the regions by the same indicators for 2017 and 2018. It turned out that the average values of the clusters are almost unchanged, while their composition may vary. The exception is the second cluster, which does not stand out in 2017.

The paper considers GRP (gross regional product) per capita as an indicator of regional well-being. An essential feature of the distribution of GRP per capita by region (see Fig. 5) is the presence of several points, the values of which are significantly higher than the average. The regions with the highest values of GRP per capita are Sakhalin Region, Tyumen Region, Chukotka Autonomous District, Moscow City, Magadan Region, Republic of Sakha (Yakutia). For these regions, the share of sales of innovative products among all sales of enterprises is relatively low, which is primarily due to the scale of regional economies and the structure of production. For other regions, there is no explicit correlation between welfare and the scale of distribution of innovative products in the market and no correlation between the market novelty of products and the scale of their distribution.

Figure 5: Histogram of the distribution of GRP per capita by Russian regions in 2018

3. The main features of regional strategies

3.1 Peculiarities of invariable strategies

The majority of Russian regional enterprises do not aspire to technology transfer. Such a situation can be connected with limited resources when the inflow of technologies, including abroad, is limited. Also, the companies possessing own sufficient resources can focus on their resources and create innovations without the attraction of outside organizations (Arkhipova et al., 2019; Balycheva and Samovoleva, 2019). Behavior characterized by low activity in the acquisition and transfer of technology is observed in the regions of the first cluster. In 2016, 64 regions belonged to this cluster, and in 2017 and 2018. - 59 regions each. At the same time, this type of behavior was unchanged in 41 Russian regions. For the regions that did not change their cluster affiliation during the period under consideration, the value of gross regional product per capita is 17% lower than the Russian average. Nevertheless, the standard deviation of this indicator from the average is quite significant, which confirms the assumption that despite the similar strategy concerning technology transfer, the reasons for not purchasing/selling technologies may differ significantly among themselves. At the same time, the scale of distribution of innovative products calculated as the share of sales of innovative products among all sales of enterprises is less than the average for Russia by 15%, and the share of new-to-market products among all sales of all innovative products is almost 2 times greater than the average (18.6% in 2018) (36.0% in 2018). Thus, significant indicators of the novelty of innovative products are achieved in this group, not due to technology transfer, including from abroad.

The most interesting are the regions of the group, the market novelty of innovative products that exceeds the average Russian values by more than two times. There are 15 such regions. Tambov Region, Krasnodar Territory, and Zabaykalsky Territory are examples. It may also be noted that the regions of the group with the highest wealth (Tyumen Region, the Sakha Republic) do not demonstrate high innovation activity. The share of sales of innovative products among all sales of regional enterprises is 3.3% and 0.8%, respectively (the national average being 6.5%), while the share of sales of products new to the market does not exceed 10% and 8%, respectively (the national average being 18.6%).

The regions of the second cluster are characterized by active cooperation with foreign partners in the creation of research and development. Besides, the region's enterprises tend to acquire ready-made technologies from abroad. For the regions following this strategy during the three years, the GRP per capita exceeds the average Russian indicator more than 4.5 times. Nevertheless, the enterprises have not yet managed to achieve a significant scale of distribution of innovative products despite relatively high market novelty indicators. Probably, it is connected with the innovation cycle (Nizhegorodtzev et al., 2017), when the period of creation of products new for the market is followed by the period of their active distribution (Golichenko, 2020).

Like the regions of the second cluster, the regions of the third cluster also focus on interaction with foreign partners. However, unlike the previous case, cooperation does not occur at the stage of research and development but is carried out through the acquisition of finished technologies abroad. As in the regions of the second cluster, the scale of distribution of innovative products in the market is not significant. At that, the average level of market novelty of products exceeds the all-Russian one almost twice. Thus, the enterprises of the regions achieve a relatively high quality of innovative products, including acquiring technologies abroad.

Enterprises of the regions of the fourth cluster have sufficient potential to sell developed technologies abroad. The enterprises also actively buy technologies abroad and interact with foreign organizations at the research and development stage. As an example of the region, which demonstrated this behavior during the three years, we can cite the Nizhny Novgorod region. It is possible to note the high quality of the innovative process of the region (Samovoleva and Balycheva, 2018), as a result of which the region manages to achieve a significant level of distribution of innovative products new for the local market of organizations.

The behavior of enterprises in the regions of the fifth cluster differs significantly from other regions. The region is characterized by large specific scales of acquisition and sale of technologies. At the same time, most technology transfer is carried out inside the country. There is also no significant cooperation in the processes of the creation of new knowledge with foreign partners. During the three years, this type of behavior was demonstrated only by the enterprises of Moscow. For two years, this type of behavior was also followed by the Tula and Kaluga regions' enterprises.

3.2 Peculiarities of variation strategies

Several Russian regions demonstrate a change in the strategy of behavior concerning technology transfer over the period under study, i.e., transitions between clusters. The first cluster, which is neutral to technology transfer, is the most stable. Nevertheless, some regions alternate periods of technology acquisition/sales with the absence of such activity. It is possible to assume that significant growth of acquisitions of technologies from abroad leads to an increase in the quality of innovative products after a specific time (Samovoleva, 2019). Moreover, that significant growth of transfer of technologies abroad can be connected with an increase in quality of innovative products in the previous periods or with the growth of expenses on research and development, connected with innovations. In the second case, the enterprises could create technology and either not bring the product on its basis to the market, or the technology can be associated with the improvement of the production process, i.e., process innovations. To test these hypotheses, we will analyze the innovative behavior of the regions demonstrating transitions between clusters over the period under study.

To test the hypothesis that the quality of innovative products of the region has increased due to the growth of activity in the acquisition of technology abroad, we considered the regions that made the transition from the first to the second and third clusters in 2017 and analyzed the dynamics of innovation activity from 2016 to 2018. For example, the Volgograd region is characterized by an increase in the propensity to use foreign technologies and a slight increase in the market novelty of innovative products in the period under study.

To test the hypothesis of significant quality of innovative products or growth of R&D costs in regions that have changed their strategy from neutral to selling technology abroad, the regions that made the transition to the fourth cluster at any of the points in time considered were examined, and their innovation activity from 2014 to 2018 was analyzed.

Table 1: Characteristics of innovation activity of regions that have made the transition to the fourth cluster

Region	Characteristics of innovative products	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Russia	Scale of distribution	9%	8%	9%	7%	7%
	Market novelty	15%	14%	15%	23%	19%
Bryansk region	Scale of distribution	7%	17%	19%	7%	3%
	Market novelty	15%	5%	2%	12%	18%
Vladimir region	Scale of distribution	8%	10%	6%	8%	4%
	Market novelty	12%	31%	27%	37%	52%
Kabardino-Balkarian Republic	Scale of distribution	2%	4%	1%	1%	1%
	Market novelty	3%	32%	95%	96%	89%
Kemerovo region	Scale of distribution	2%	3%	2%	2%	1%
	Market novelty	51%	31%	42%	54%	5%
Omsk region	Scale of distribution	4%	4%	3%	3%	2%
	Market novelty	42%	45%	20%	20%	9%
Komi Republic	Scale of distribution	5%	3%	2%	0,3%	1%
	Market novelty	3%	31%	10%	54%	88%
Republic of Mordovia	Scale of distribution	27%	27%	27%	27%	24%
	Market novelty	25%	26%	9%	9%	9%

It turned out that the regions that made the transition to the fourth cluster, which is characterized by the sale of technology abroad, are focused on the production of innovative products new to the market. Simultaneously, they do not manage to establish large-scale production of innovative products new for the local market of organizations sales. This fact is evidenced by the low shares of sales of innovative products among all sales of enterprises. The exception is the Republic of Mordovia, whose share of innovative products exceeds the national average three times (see Table 1). It may also be noted that the welfare of all regions that have made the transition to the fourth cluster, except for the Komi Republic, has the level of welfare below the national average.

4. Linking technology transfer and internal research and development

This section analyzes the relationship between research and development costs and technology acquisition costs. The dynamics of this relationship are also investigated to find the overall effect (substitution or supplementation) in Russian regions.

For Russia, on average, the share of research and development costs exceeds the share of technology acquisition costs by 30%. To conduct the analysis and obtain comparable results, all expenses are reduced to one base year, and the expenses for research and development are multiplied by the coefficient characterizing the change in the volume of expenses over time. Thus, as a result, adjusted data on the volume of research and development costs are obtained, allowing us to understand the overall effect of addition or substitution.

The country is characterized by a slight predominance of the substitution effect when acquired technologies replace the need for own research and development. This situation takes place against the background of a decrease in the volume of expenses from 2015 to 2018, both for research and development and for the acquisition of technologies. Despite the slight predominance of the substitution effect on average, many regions show an increase in the relative costs of research and development, while the volume of investments in technology acquisition remains unchanged. For such regions, whose prosperity is not higher than the all-Russian one, the acquisition of technologies allows increasing their research potential. The Astrakhan and Ryazan regions can be given as examples.

5. Conclusions

As a result of the study, it was possible to identify five predominant strategies for the technology transfer of enterprises in the Russian regions. It was found that during 2016-2018 there were five stable strategies. Part of the regions turned out to be unchanged in the choice of strategy. Other regions were subject to its change. Most Russian regions proved to be inactive in acquiring and transferring technology both within and outside the country.

In some cases, the reason is limited resources, leading to the lack of opportunities to improve the quality of the innovation process through the acquired technologies, including those acquired abroad. Also, companies in other regions, having sufficient resources, may not focus on the developments of third-party organizations and create innovations without the involvement of acquired technologies. This strategy belongs to the most stable; regions are the least eager to change it. Nevertheless, there are regions that alternate periods of technology acquisition/sales with the absence of such activity. Thus, significant growth of technology acquisitions from abroad leads to an increase in the quality of innovative products after a certain period.

In contrast, the growth of technology transfer abroad may be associated with an increase in the quality of innovative products in previous periods or increased research and development costs associated with innovation. In the second case, companies could create technology and either not introduce a product based on it to the market, or the technology could be related to the improvement of the production process, i.e., process innovations. The second and third strategies aim to attract foreign knowledge through the acquisition of ready-made technologies abroad or participation in joint research and development projects with foreign organizations. The sale of technology abroad characterizes the fourth strategy despite the small overall scale of the transfer. The regions whose enterprises are committed to this strategy are characterized by significant indicators of the market novelty of innovative products, which, combined with the transfer of technology abroad, indicates a high quality of innovative products produced. Nevertheless, the enterprises fail to achieve their significant distribution in the local market. The fifth strategy is characterized by a significant scale of transfer within the country.

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